

GLOBAL WARMING

Tara Singh

A-1502 Sea Queen Heritage, Plot-6, Sec-18, Sanpada, Navi Mumbai- 400705

Mob. +91-9322991198, email: swargvibha@gmail.com

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Abstract

Changes in the Earth's atmosphere have increased temperatures by about one degree Celsius over the past 100 years, resulting in changes in rainfall patterns, melting icebergs and glaciers, rising sea levels, and impacts on flora and fauna. Climate change in India is having profound effects on India, which is ranked fourth among the list of countries most affected by climate change in the period from 1996 to 2015. India emits about 3 gigatons (Gt) CO₂ eq of greenhouse gases each year; about two and a half tons per person, which is less than the world average. The country emits 7% of global emissions, despite having 17% of the world population. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC); the efforts were made to control and stabilize the concentration of greenhouse gases. The UNFCCC entered into force on Mar. 21, 1994, and has been ratified by 197 countries. The UNFCCC sets a long-term objective of avoiding dangerous human interference with the climate system. It is extremely required to control the reason for global warming for everyone's life.

Key words: Global Warming

Global warming means "increased temperature of the earth and due to it changes in weather". Today the whole world as a whole is worried and troubled by this problem. Changes in the Earth's atmosphere have increased temperatures by about one degree Celsius over the past 100 years, resulting in changes in rainfall patterns, melting icebergs and glaciers, rising sea levels, and impacts on flora and fauna.

The rate of warming of the earth is increasing every year. It has been forecasted that the last two decades of the 21st century will be the warmest in the last 400 years, according to the United Nations' Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). A report on has also been issued, according to which, eleven of the last 12 years have been the warmest since 1850.

Impact on ice-caps and glaciers

According to the report after a study conducted by the Multinational Arctic Climate Impact Assessment between 2000-2004, the average temperature of Alaska, compared to eastern Russia and western Canada, has increased twice as much as the increase in global average temperature. Apart from this, on top of glaciers and mountains around the world the frozen ice is melting fast. An example of this is the Montano Glacier National Park located in the northern hemisphere. Where there were 150 glaciers in 1910, now only about 30 are left. If the amount of carbon dioxide continues to increase on the earth at this speed, then after 15 years there will not be a single glacier left. This is the story of the North Pole as well. Here in the last 30 years, the layer of ice has thinned, while its expansion has also decreased by ten percent.

Reasons for increasing greenhousegases

There are many reasons for the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, including long-lasting factories that produce industrial gases. Rapid deforestation, has led to global warming as trees

absorb carbon dioxide and act as natural carbon sink. Population growth is also a major cause of global warming, as a greater number of people mean more fossil fuels and energy will be used. The higher the amount of greenhouse in the atmosphere, the more radiation it will trap, due to which the temperature on the surface of the earth will gradually increase. Apart from this, the emissions from the eruption of volcanoes also contribute to the increase in global warming. According to an estimate, during the 150 years of the industrial age, the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere has increased by 31 percent. Over the same years, agricultural activities, mainly animal husbandry and rice growing, have increased the level of methane in the atmosphere by 151 percent.

Indian perspective

Climate change in India is having profound effects on India, which is ranked fourth among the list of countries most affected by climate change in the period from 1996 to 2015. India emits about 3 gigatons (Gt) CO₂eq of greenhouse gases each year; about two and a half tons per person, which is less than the world average. The country emits 7% of global emissions, despite having 17% of the world population. Temperature rises on the Tibetan Plateau are causing Himalayan glaciers to retreat, threatening the flow rate of the Ganges, Brahmaputra, Yamuna and other major rivers. A 2007 World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) report states that the Indus River may run dry for the same reason. Heat waves' frequency and power are increasing in India because of climate change. Severe landslides and floods are projected to become increasingly common in such states as Assam. The Indira Gandhi Institute of Development Research has reported that, if the predictions relating to global warming made by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change come to fruition, climate-related factors could cause India's GDP to decline by up to 9%. Contributing to this there would be shifting growing seasons for major crops such as rice, production of which could fall by 40%

Global Initiatives

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

The first international effort to stop climate change due to global warming emerged in 1992 in the form of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). In this, efforts were made to control and stabilize the concentration of greenhouse gases. The UNFCCC entered into force on Mar. 21, 1994, and has been ratified by 197 countries.

The UNFCCC sets a long-term objective of avoiding dangerous human interference with the climate system. Toward that end, the agreement:

- commits all nations to take steps to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions;
- establishes the principle of "common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities" (CBDRRC), recognizing that countries vary in their contributions to climate change and capacities to address it, so their obligations will likewise vary; and
- commits developed countries to assist developing countries in reducing emissions and coping with climate impacts.

Governed by the Conference of Parties (COP), which meets annually, the UNFCCC serves as the foundation of an evolving global climate effort.

Kyoto Protocol

At COP 1 in 1995, UNFCCC parties decided to accelerate climate efforts by launching negotiations toward a first sub-agreement. They agreed that, consistent with the principle of CBDRRC, (principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities (CBDRRC), the new agreement would establish binding targets and timetables for reducing developed country emissions, but no new commitments for developing countries.

The Kyoto Protocol, which was signed in 1997 and ran from 2005 to 2020, was the first implementation of measures under the UNFCCC.

The treaty established different responsibilities for three categories of signatory states. These categories are developed countries, developed countries with special financial responsibilities, and developing countries. The developed countries, also called Annex 1 countries, are called upon to adopt national policies and take corresponding measures on the mitigation of climate change by limiting their anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases as well as to report on steps adopted with the aim of returning individually or jointly to their 1990 emissions levels. The developed countries with special financial

responsibilities are also called Annex II countries. They include all of the Annex I countries with the exception of those in transition to democracy and market economies. Annex II countries are called upon to provide new and additional financial resources to meet the costs incurred by developing countries in complying with their obligation to produce national inventories of their emissions by sources and their removals by sinks for all greenhouse gases not controlled by the Montreal Protocol.

The Kyoto Protocol applied to the seven greenhouse gases listed in Annex A: carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆), Nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃). Nitrogen trifluoride was added for the second compliance period during the Doha Round.

The Protocol's first commitment period started in 2008 and ended in 2012. All 36 countries that fully participated in the first commitment period complied with the Protocol. However, nine countries had to resort to the flexibility mechanisms by funding emission reductions in other countries because their national emissions were slightly greater than their targets. The financial crisis of 2007-08 helped reduce the emissions.

A second commitment period was agreed to in 2012 to extend the agreement to 2020, known as the Doha Amendment to the Kyoto Protocol, in which 37 countries had binding targets: Australia, the European Union (and its then 28 member states, now 27), Belarus, Iceland, Kazakhstan, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland, and Ukraine.

Paris Agreement

The Paris Agreement is a legally binding international treaty on climate change. It was adopted by 196 Parties at COP 21 in Paris, on 12 December 2015 and entered into force on 4 November 2016.

Its goal is to limit global warming to well below 2, preferably to 1.5 degrees Celsius, compared to pre-industrial levels.

To achieve this long-term temperature goal, countries aim to reach global peaking of greenhouse gas emissions as soon as possible to achieve a climate neutral world by mid-century.

The Paris Agreement is a landmark in the multilateral climate change process because, for the first time, a binding agreement brings all nations into a common cause to undertake ambitious efforts to combat climate change and adapt to its effects.

Implementation of the Paris Agreement requires economic and social transformation, based on the best available science. The Paris Agreement works on a 5- year cycle of increasingly ambitious climate action carried out by countries. By 2020, countries

submit their plans for climate action known as nationally determined contributions (NDCs).

COP26, Glasgow Climate Pact, UK 2021

COP26 introduced a broad, political “cover decision” – the “Glasgow Climate Pact” – calling for renewed efforts to raise ambition on cutting emissions, climate finance, adaptation and the loss and damage already being caused by warming.

The pact “requests” countries to raise their ambition again next year and creates a “Glasgow Dialogue” on funding for loss and damage, as well as pledging to double adaptation finance.

It is also the first-ever COP decision to explicitly target action against fossil fuels, calling for a “phasedown of unabated coal” and “phase-out” of “inefficient” fossil-fuel subsidies.

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